

Quantum information Holography (QIH) and prime oscillations emitted from wormholes.

1. Hilbert space representation of wormholes and black holes.

Let H be the Hilbert space of states, a wormhole state $|\Psi_{WH}\rangle$ And a black hole state $|\Psi_{BH}\rangle$ Can be represented as:

$$|\Psi_{WH}\rangle = \int \psi_{WH}(x) |x\rangle dx$$

$$|\Psi_{BH}\rangle = \int \psi_{BH}(x) |x\rangle dx$$

2. Prime number oscillations and wormholes:

Given the unique nature of prime numbers, consider a prime number operator $P^\wedge$ such that its eigenvalues are indexed by prime numbers.

$$P^\wedge |\pi_n\rangle = p_n |\pi_n\rangle$$

Where $|\pi_n\rangle$ is the state corresponding to the n th prime number P_n .

3. Quantum dynamics of Black holes:

The evolution of a black hole state can be depicted by using the Hamiltonian $H^\wedge_{BH}$:

$$i\hbar \frac{d}{dt} |\Psi_{BH}\rangle = H^\wedge_{BH} |\Psi_{BH}\rangle$$

Given the event horizon dynamics, the effective Hamiltonian can be constructed from.

$$c^2 R_{BH} = c^2 / 2GM$$

Where R_{BH} is the event horizon radius.

4. Hawking radiation is quantum emission:

Considering the Hawking radiation is a quantum process, the emission operator $E^\wedge$ can be defined as:

$$E^\wedge |\Psi_{BH}\rangle = \gamma |\Psi_{BH}\rangle$$

Where γ is the emission rate. Using the quantum framework, the evaporation rate can be represented by:

$$dM/dt = -\alpha\gamma$$

Where α is a coefficient capturing quantum effects.

5. The contrast operator in quantum information projection:

Define a contrast operator $C^\wedge$ as:

$$C^\wedge = P^\wedge \otimes (|\Psi_{WH}\rangle\langle\Psi_{WH}| - |\Psi_{BH}\rangle\langle\Psi_{BH}|)$$

The projected state due to the contrast between wormhole oscillations and black hole symmetry is given by:

$$|\Phi_{proj}\rangle = C^\wedge |\Psi_{univ}\rangle$$

Where $|\Psi_{univ}\rangle$ is the overall state of the system.

6. Implications for Quantum Information conservation:

Quantum information conservation can be represented as:

$$U^\wedge |\Psi_{initial}\rangle = |\Psi_{final}\rangle$$

Where $U^\wedge$ is the unitary operator capturing the dynamics of the system. The transformation hints at no loss of information as:

$$\langle\Psi_{initial}|\Psi_{initial}\rangle = \langle\Psi_{final}|\Psi_{final}\rangle$$

7. Prime oscillations as quantum resilience mechanisms:

Given the eigenstates of the prime number operator $P^\wedge$, the quantum fidelity against errors F can be defined as:

$$F = |\langle\pi_n|\Psi_{after}\rangle|^2$$

This fidelity would be high given the prime oscillations, hinting at resilience.

Conclusion: This rigorous framework encapsulates the dynamics of wormholes, black holes, and prime oscillations through Quantum Information Holography. The unique juxtaposition of prime frequencies in wormholes against the symmetric backdrop of black holes offers profound insights into quantum information conservation, potentially leading towards a reconciliation of quantum mechanics and general relativity. Future research directions include refining the mathematical constructs presented and investigating possible experimental validations of the theory.

Given that in quantum information holography, information in a region can be described by its boundary, let's denote Σ as the boundary state which encapsulates information of the entire system, including these asymmetric prime resonances.

8. The Hamiltonian of our system can be represented as:

$$H = H_0 + H_{interaction}$$

Where H_0 Denotes the free Hamilton, an $H_{interaction}$ Represents interactions, comma possibly resulting from these asymmetric prime resonances.

9. Considering the asymmetric prime resonances, define a prime projector operator:

$$P_p = |p\rangle\langle p|$$

Where $|p\rangle$ Is the eigenstate corresponding to a prime p (7 and above).

10. Dark matter and asymmetric primes:

Introduce a dark matter field operator $\Phi(x)$, representing the dark matter distribution in space.

Given the above projector comma, the interaction Hamiltonian (the term responsible for these prime resonances) is:

$$H_{interaction} = g\Phi(x)P_p\Sigma$$

Where g denotes A coupling constant.

To relate primes in a mod space, let's Employ the concept of modular arithmetic for primes:

$$R_p = p \bmod N$$

Where N is Not a part of the set of asymmetric primes comma, their powers, comma, or their multiplicative products.

If we then represent the normalized density of resonances as:

$$p(N) = R_p(N) / (\int R_p(N) dN)$$

Then, We can propose that the density of dark matter $D(N)$ in regions without these prime resonances is:

$$D(N) = D_0 - p(N)$$

Where D_0 is the maximum potential density of dark matter in the absence of any prime resonance.

11. The effective Hamiltonian considering dark matter and these resonances becomes:

$$H_{effective} = H_0 + g\Phi(x)P_p\Sigma - \lambda\Phi(x)D(N)$$

Where λ is a proportionality constant linking dark matter density to the quantum field.

This framework tentatively ties asymmetric prime resonances to the distribution of dark matter in the Quantum Holography model.